

LABOR RELATIONS IN AGRICULTURE AND THEIR THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

Tolanov Dilyorbek

Andijan Institute of Agriculture and agrotechnologies

Lecturer in the Department of Economics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10911229>

Abstract. In the article, innovative ways of improving labor relations in agricultural enterprises of our country, in turn, serve to further increase the efficiency of resource-saving technologies. As a result of this, the increase in the volume of product production, the increase in real incomes, the creation of a competitive environment in the industry, the reduction of costs, the reduction of costs, the reduction of excessive expenses, the maximum profit at the lowest cost, the demand for the product being produced, the productive use of our limited land, production to the increase of the added value of the manufactured product, the work of in-depth study of the manufactured product is analyzed

Key words: added value, product, quality indicators, real income, profit, material cost, enterprise activity, cultivated area, gross product, productivity

INTRODUCTION. Innovative directions for improving labor relations in agricultural enterprises of our country in turn serve to further increase the efficiency of resource-efficient technologies. Thanks to this, the increase in the volume of production of products, the increase in real revenues, the formation of a competitive environment in the field, the reduction of costs, the reduction of costs, the reduction of costs, the reduction of the cost, the maximum benefit from the deficit, the increase in taste for the product being produced, the unprecedented use of our limited land, the increase In this regard, new ideas, new advanced technologies, disciplines in a new direction will come from new departments will be separated.

Peoples and countries that are able to create conditions for the formation of high-quality human potential are always in a leading position in the world, and with its help have developed and mastered the most advanced products and technologies for their time. This can be clearly observed throughout the history of human development - from the beginning of the Neolithic period to the present day.

In the conditions of modernization of the economy, innovations in the production process, the introduction of modern information technologies are leading to the emergence of Labor Organization, new knowledge-oriented sectors of the economy. The formation and development of the innovative sector of the economy creates the need for the emergence of innovative types of Labor, the origin of innovative employment, the development of innovation in social Labor Relations. This requires cadres to improve their skills, skills, initiative, and develop new ideas.

At the moment, the Republic of Uzbekistan has a number of problems on the issue of employment of working-age labor resources in terms of Labor potential. In order to increase the level of employment of students, a number of decisions are made and reforms are carried out. For example, the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 27,

2017 No. 3151 "on measures to further expand the sectors and sectors of the economy in the training of specialists in higher education and improving the quality of Management" covers a wide range of tasks facing higher educational institutions and employers.

The importance of labor resources is great in meeting all the requirements of our country for agricultural products. For the implementation of the agricultural production process, material, labor and capital resources must be available. Within these resources, labor is an active resource, connecting the other two resources with each other, and its level affects the results of the production process.

Labor is a conscious, goal-oriented activity of a person. The production process requires the effective harmonization of human labor, objects and means of Labor, natural conditioning. Man employs these means of production in a certain area, period, and carries out the production process. Including plowing, preparation for planting, planting, watering, processing, harvesting, etc. The effect of the production process depends, first of all, on the knowledge, qualifications, attitude to work, moreover, on the development of Science and technology, on the quality, state of the means of production and, finally, on natural conditions of the labor resource. Therefore, a person should focus his activities on the effective employment of all of them wisely, competently. Labor is thus an economic category. Its nature is determined by the relations of production. Therefore, boigan, who has the ability to meet demand, is directly dependent on the conscious activity of a person, that is, on his labor, to grow agricultural products, to perform services.

In agriculture, labor resources include men between the ages of 16 and 60 who have the ability to work, boigan women between the ages of 16 and 55, and adolescents and pensioners who are shugiling with labor activities at their discretion. In agriculture, adolescents are mainly involved in seasonal work.

In agriculture, due to the sectoral characteristics of labor resources, there are the following distinctive features:

- labor and its effect are related to natural conditions;
- the use of the labor resource is greatly influenced by the seasonality of agricultural production;
- the process of labor in agriculture is inextricably linked with living organisms;
- the level of mechanization and automation of the labor process in agriculture is low;
- the labor process in the network is not specialized in a narrow range;
- the growth rate of the number of labor resources in rural areas is relatively high, etc.

The highlighted features directly affect the amount, quality and effect of Labor spent on the network. Natural conditions, that is, the climate and the state of the feed, directly affect the efficiency of the labor resource. In the winter months, the demand for the labor resource sharply decreases, and in the spring and harvest, the demand for it increases. During the same period, seasonal workers are required to attract on a contractual basis. Employees working in agriculture and animal husbandry should know the characteristics of the plants and livestock. The fact that the network is not provided at the required level with new, productive techniques does not allow the complete mechanization of certain work processes (watering, uniting, harvesting, feeding livestock, milking, etc.), as a result of which live labor costs are high. In order to ensure its effectiveness in the implementation of the labor process in agriculture, it is advisable to take into account all the features.

In the study of Labor Relations and their theoretical foundations in agriculture, we must dwell on the terms that define labor and Labor Relations.

LABOR RELATIONS - it is a social and labor relationship that occurs on the basis of an employment contract and is regulated by labor law, according to which one subject - employee is obliged to perform an labor function, observing the rules of the internal Labor procedure, and the other - the employer is obliged to provide labor, provide healthy and safe working conditions and pay for his labor in accordance.

Labor relations are characterized by certain characteristics inherent in it.

Characteristic features that make it possible to distinguish Labor Relations from related, including civil-legal ones, include the following.

1. A personal feature of the rights and obligations of an employee who is forced to participate in the production or other activities of an organization (employer) only by his own labor. The employee has no right to be the representative of another employee in his place or to delegate his work to another, just as the employer has no right to replace the employee with another, except in cases established by law (for example, in an employment contract, the employee is not at work due to illness, etc.). There are no such restrictions in civil law, in which the contractor has the right to attract other persons to perform work.

2. An employee is obliged to perform a certain, predetermined Labor function (work in a particular specialty, qualification or position), but does not perform a specific task individually (separately) on a specific date. The latter are typical for civil-legal obligations associated with labor activity, the purpose of which is to obtain a certain labor result (product), to carry out a certain task or service on a certain date.

3. The peculiarity of Labor Relations is also in the fact that the performance of the Labor function is carried out in the conditions of general (cooperative) labor, which requires the subjects of Labor Relations to obey the internal labor rules established by the organization. (employer). The performance of the Labor function and the internal subordination associated with the work order means the involvement of citizens in labor (labor collective) organizations. All three features noted in this paragraph, in contrast to the subject of civil-legal relations, constitute the characteristic features of a citizen's work as an employee. As you know, a single and complex labor law attitude combines both coordinating and subordinate elements, where freedom of Labor is combined with subordination to internal labor rules.

4. The uncompensated nature of Labor Relations is manifested in the organization's (employer's) response to the performance of work - in payment. wages are usually in cash. A distinctive feature of Labor Relations is that the payment is paid for the spent living Labor regularly carried out by the employee within the specified period. working time, and as in civil-legal relations, is the specific result of materialized (past) Labor, and not for the performance of a specific task or service.

5. A characteristic sign of Labor Relations is also the right of each of the subjects to end this relationship without any sanctions in the prescribed manner. At the same time, in established cases, the employer is obliged to notify the employee of his dismissal on his initiative and pay the severance allowance in the manner prescribed by labor law.

The main obligations of the employer can be grouped as follows: a) to provide employment in accordance with the established Labor function and, accordingly, to ensure the

actual employment of this employee as the executor of the Labor function, as well as to create conditions that ensure its effective implementation;

b) ensuring healthy and safe working conditions provided for by labor law, collective agreement and agreement of the parties;

v) payment of wages in accordance with the amount provided for by the contract, taking into account the complexity of Labor and the quality of labor, as well as the provision of warranty and compensation payments;d) xodimning ijtimoiy va maishiy ehtiyojlarini qondirish.

Innovative production is the main way and the technical and technological basis for a sharp increase in the standard of living of the population. The analysis shows that our achievements in the field of economy are due to high costs, the expenditure of additional funds, low production of finished products in the structure of products produced in the sectors and sectors of the real sector of the economy, mainly the production of natural raw materials and their export. The fact that the volume of products produced in an innovative way accounts for an extremely low percentage of GDP, economic efficiency, low labor productivity indicators still remain relevant. From the above points, we want to say that we consider it necessary to adapt certain aspects of the innovative policy being pursued in the Republic to the spirit of the Times, that is, to further improve. From economic practice it is known that we think that further improvement of investment, taxes and taxation, customs, financial and credit, directions of innovative policies and their effectiveness will create an appropriate legal, organizational and economic basis for the provision of sustainable economic growth in innovative ways.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS.

Employment, unemployment, inflation, labor market problems and their fundamental research on the basis of a mathematical apparatus in the conditions of a developed market economy: J.M.Keynes, A.Oswald, H.Roseanne, F.Haek, S.Hall, K.A number of scientific works of leading foreign economists such as Yanosh are dedicated. These studies serve as a theoretical basis for studying the general problems of the labor market and their prospects in developed countries with a market-oriented economy . Moreover, the development of Economics in this field of science is influenced by the countries of the CIS: B.D.Breev, T.I.Zaslavskaya, V.G.Kostikov, A.A.Nikiforova, G.S.Well-known scientists like Strumilin are also adding a decent share¹.

The study of these problems was carried out by the OECD.X.Abdurahmanov, S.S.Gulomov, L.P.Maksakova, R.A.Ubaydullaeva, N.Khojaev, R.X.A number of scientific works of Shodiev, T. Sh.Shodiev and other scientists are also dedicated².

Бреев Б.Д., Жаромский В.С., Галецкий В.Ф. Оценка масштабов потенциальной безработицы на основе методики "Кривой Филлипса" //Моделирование рыночных отношений и социальная политика: Отв.ред. А.Ю. Шевяков. - М.: ЦЭМИ РАН, 1993. С.82- 102.; Заславская Т.И., Рывкина Р.В. Методологические проблемы системного изучения деревни.- Новосибирск: Наука, 1977.- 315 с.; Костиков В.Г. Проблемы занятости и формирования рынка труда //Экономика и математические методы.Т. 26. Вып.5.- М., 1990. С.803-817.; Струмилин Г.С. Проблемы экономики труда.- М.; Наука, 1982.471 с.; Никифорова А.А. Рынок труда: занятость и безработица. М.: Международные отношения, 1991.- 184 с.

Also, the income of employees working in modern technology increases. As a result, its consumption demand also increases. together with this, there are also the following factors that affect the change in labor demand:

1. Complementarity between Labor and technology. When workers are engaged in labor activities with a machine gun, the demand for such workers and the amount of wages increases. If workers are performing tasks that can only be performed by machines, their role can be filled with techniques. This creates a shift in demand for labor as a result of the introduction of new technology.

2. Flexibility of providing labor. Even if the demand for programs provided by the software developer increases, there is no significant change in employment until skilled workers are adequately provided. The increase in wages of software development professionals and researchers increases and stimulates labor supply. However, the flexibility of the demand for highly skilled labor can lead to the fact that the large number of employees in the quality of a software developer will lead to a decrease in wages.

3. Improve personnel skills. The use of innovative technologies of a new type in automation and economy will increase the demand for highly qualified, modern knowledge personnel. The imbalance between the capabilities of the labor force and technologies prevents the increase in labor productivity, slowing the change in employment and wages in labor.

RESULTS. The formation of innovative directions of improving labor relations at enterprises in agriculture economic development and the interdepartmental movement of employment have a correct dependence on investments in the sectors of the network. In addition, the penetration of new technologies, advanced experiences, highly qualified specialists into various industries and industries, regions along with investment will ensure the rapid development of entrepreneurship.

To this end, Uzbekistan has developed goals and objectives such as reducing state participation in the economy, increasing new jobs through the rapid development of the private sector, modernizing and diversifying the economy, ensuring effective employment, high economic growth by increasing labor productivity.

CONCLUSION. Without innovations and new ideas, the current development of the economy cannot be imagined. At a time when in the total population there is an increase in the Salm of working age or a trend towards a decrease in the burden of immortality, this situation can lead to two different consequences:

one – as a result of not establishing effective use of them, the problem of unemployment is gaining relevance;

second – significant economic growth can be achieved through the effective use of those of increasing working age. In this case, it is required to focus on increasing the share of employment in the economically active population, their employment in productive labor, and in order to develop the economy innovatively, it is advisable to use the model of labor market management and the proposed mechanism of the integrated socioeconomic cluster structure. Thus, the most important thing is that the timely and correct choice of a particular profession becomes the basis for achieving high efficiency in production, saves the capital spent on training personnel, develops human thinking, encourages it to manifest itself, fulfill its civic duty, lead a prosperous life. Such a person is satisfied with active participation in public

affairs, the fruits of his work, receives great spiritual encouragement. The most important thing is that he lives satisfied with life.

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